

EXPERIENCES AND PROCESSES ON ENRICHMENT LEARNING ACTIVITIES IN MATHEMATICS AND THE PROBLEM-SOLVING SKILLS OF GRADE 9 STUDENTS

ROBINSON M. LOMIBAO Jr.¹

DELON A. CHING²

robinson.lomibao@deped.gov.ph¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0002-1314-7832¹

0000-0003-1435-4371²

San Pablo City Integrated High School, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

In the implementation of the K-12 Program, the twin goals of Mathematics are critical thinking and problem-solving skills that will serve as the focal point in learning Mathematics. Enrichment promotes problem-solving skills which improve student's ability to concentrate and make learning more valuable and rewarding. Enrichment activities help students to become more engaged in their learning and to retain more knowledge. To support, this study introduced the Enrichment Experiences and Activities which measured its effect in improving the Problem-solving Skills of the students. Descriptive research design- led in attaining the objectives of the study participated by 48 grade 9 students of San Pablo City Integrated High School of the academic year 2020-2021. The result of the study revealed that there are structured enrichment learning activities provided to the students considering the exploratory activity, training activity, and investigation of real problems during Mathematics class. However, there is no significant relationship depicted between the extent of structured Enrichment Learning activities and the level of problem-solving skills of the student-respondents. Lastly, as to the process of enrichment learning activities, it posited a significant relationship primarily a well-managed process of facilitation and feedbacking helps students to be very satisfactory in interpreting and concluding, a well-managed process coaching makes it more feasible to achieve a very satisfactory level in understanding, planning and solving. The study suggests that the use of enrichment activities in Mathematics cater a positive effect to enhance the Mathematical ability and problem-solving skills of the students.

Keywords: Experiences, Enrichment Activities, Mathematical Skills, Problem-solving skills